

PREVELANCE OF TENSION NECK SYNDROME AMONG YOUNG ADULTS USING MOBILE PHONES

Dr. Sajawal Hussain^{*1}, Dr. Noor ul Ain², Dr. Aqsa Ali Khan³, Dr. Hafiz M. Ammad Khan⁴,
Dr. Nabila Shah⁵, Dr. Faizan Rehman⁶

^{*1}Doctor of Physical Therapy (DPT) Department of Physiotherapy University of Balochistan, Quetta
²DPT-MS (OMPT) Faculty of Rehabilitation and allied health sciences Riphah International University
Lahore
³Doctor of Physical Therapy (DPT) Department of Physiotherapy University of Balochistan, Quetta
^{4,5,6}Doctor of Physical Therapy Department of Physiotherapy University of Balochistan, Quetta

^{*1}sajawalh151214@gmail.com, ²noorulainkhan913@gmail.com, ³aksa85216@gmail.com,
⁴ammad.khan2701@gmail.com, ⁵nabilashah567@gmail.com, ⁶faizanrehman6767@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14881212>

ABSTRACT.

Tension neck syndrome is the one of the most common problem in recent eras due to increased use of mobile phone specially after the covid-19 pandemic and due to availability of all the tools needed in daily life. The tension neck syndrome is characterized by the neck pain sometimes radiating to neck, shoulders and upper back, mainly the involvement of trapezius and sternocleidomastoid muscle of neck, this pain is caused by the tension created due to the prolong flexed neck posture during mobile usage. Previous studies show that the force experienced by the cervical spine at different level of neck flexion is dramatically increased with the increased degree of flexion, normal weight of adult head is 10-12 pounds as the neck is flexed to 15 degrees the weight experienced by cervical spine (CS) is increased to 27 pounds and ultimately to 60 pounds at 60 degree of cervical flexion. To find out the prevalence of Tension Neck Syndrome among young mobile phone users.

To assess the level of awareness/knowledge of tension neck syndrome and find association between time duration and neck disability. A cross-sectional study was conducted. For the study NDI questionnaire and mobile phone addiction scale MAS was used to collect data from the participants. The sample size was calculated by using RAO Software and data was analyzed by statistical package for social sciences SPSS 21.0 software to calculate the frequencies and association between variables.

The results showed that 54% of the participants were having minimal or no difficulty 33% were having moderate disability and 11% were having severe disability and only 1% were in the crippled stage. The significance p value >0.001 shows the correlation between the time period of mobile phone usage and neck disability variable.

Based on the results of the current investigation, about half of the individuals had neck issues. Neck issues were substantially correlated with smartphone addiction. Postural education and other initiatives to raise awareness of responsible smartphone use are advised. Participating actively in sports, social activities, and physical activity during free time will help university students reduce smartphone misuse and the effects it has on neck pain. Future research is necessary to determine how well neck posture-promoting strategies work to lessen smartphone addiction and misuse, which in turn helps to relieve neck pain

Keywords: Tension Neck Syndrome, Neck Pain, Cervical Pain, Neck and Shoulder pain

The Research of Medical Science Review

INTRODUCTION

Neck Syndrome (TNS) is characterized by neck pain, shoulder pain accompanied by muscle stiffness, muscle tenderness and muscle spasm. The sensitive areas of the muscle known as trigger points leads to the pain and discomfort which often radiates to the nearby areas such as the head, neck, the shoulder and the upper back.

The symptoms include headaches radiating from the neck, neck discomfort, tightness, weariness, and stiffness in the shoulder and neck muscles, without a history of injury, ruptured cervical disk, or degenerative processes. Palpable hardening areas, tender spots, and spasm on the trapezius or sternocleidomastoid muscles may be discovered during the physical examination. These muscles are often linked to pain on the resisted side of the neck along with reduced range of motion in the neck's extension, rotation, and flexion.

A common sign of TNS is persistent neck pain, which is defined as pain in the neck that persists for longer than three months.

The use of mobile phone and portable gadgets have been increased sufficiently specifically after covid-19. The dependency on mobile phone is increasing day by day because of the all the feature available in it for our daily needs. 2-

According to a comprehensive evaluation of 15 publications, neck-related musculoskeletal problems were the most common among mobile device users (17.3–67.8%). According to two studies, the prevalence of text neck syndrome was 42.5% in India and 43.6% in Pakistan. Two more studies involving mobile phone users at Aljouf University and Qassim University in Saudi Arabia revealed that, respectively, 71.2% and 59.5% reported having cervical pain. Numerous research investigations have documented a noteworthy correlation between neck pain and addiction to smartphones.4

While it is evident that the neck is the region where smartphone users experience the most discomfort there hasn't been much research done on the ergonomic variables that contribute to neck pain in smartphone users. It is well recognized that there are several contributing causes to neck pain, with head and spinal posture being among the most crucial ones.

According to earlier research, extended neck flexion is strongly linked to neck pain in both the general population and office workers who use computers. Similarly, when using a smartphone to view its visual display terminal for extended periods of time, users typically adopt the neck flexion position.

When using a smartphone, users often keep their head flexion between 33 and 45 degrees vertical (Lee, Kang, et al. 2015). Additionally, a study by Ning et al. (2015) showed that when using a smartphone, participants maintained noticeably greater neck flexion (44.7~). When the head is flexed forward to different degrees, the weight on the spine dramatically increases; an adult head weighs 10 to 12 pounds in its neutral posture. Forces on the neck increase when the head tilts forward to 27 pounds at 15 degrees, 40 pounds at 30 degrees, 49 pounds at 45 degrees, and 60 pounds at 60 degrees. Users of the visual display terminal must bend their neck further to use it, which increases the activity of the shoulder muscles. 5- In the general population, neck discomfort has a lifetime frequency of 14–70%, making it a prevalent musculoskeletal issue. The fourth-highest number of years spent with a handicap is reported in the Global Burden of Disease report. Researchers have been motivated to examine the incidence of neck discomfort and the risk factors linked to it in the general population due to the direct and indirect economic expenses connected with it. While there is a chance that acute episodes of neck discomfort will go away entirely, they often return and become chronic. It is more frequent than previously believed for acute neck discomfort to not heal well. The risk factors for cervical discomfort are usually subtle. They are typically multifactorial, including one or more of the following: personal (age, BMI, genome, etc.), ergonomic (excessive physical activity, application of force and vibration, bad posture, repetitive movement). According to several studies, women are more likely than males to experience neck discomfort. The degenerative changes and neck discomfort are more common in elderly females. There might be a difference in definitions, such as the location and length of neck discomfort, which accounts for the disparate findings of observational research. Differences in response rates, non-comparable demographic samples, and overall study quality are examples of methodological variations that might be the reason. Furthermore, prejudice may result from it, which would explain the disparities. The fundamental reason determines whether pain is acute or persistent. Its

The Research of Medical Science Review

duration exceeds three months if it is chronic in nature. Sharp or dull pain might be experienced in a certain position. While certain cases may persist for several days or weeks, others may not. The neck is always the initial site of discomfort, and it can spread to the head, shoulders, and chest in addition to other adjacent locations. As such, other symptoms may coexist with pain. 7-8

The number of individuals utilizing smart gadgets and web-based communication has increased significantly in the last few years due to increased reliance on them. A poll conducted between 2016 and 2021 found that six billion individuals used smartphones worldwide, and many more are expected to do so in the years to come. The nations with the highest smartphone usage rates were determined be the USA, India, and the People's Republic of China.9-11

According to systematic research (which highlighted that smartphone users suffered from musculoskeletal symptoms at a rate ranging from 1% to 67.8%), neck and backaches are the most common symptom among smartphone users. Head and neck conditions accounted for the largest share of these, ranging from 59.6% of students reported having neck discomfort, 52.82% had shoulder pain, and 54.4% reported upper back pain, according to the survey. Tongo et al. (2017) observed that prolonged use of the affected upper extremities in a stationary posture during texting, web browsing, and gaming on such smart gadgets may be the cause of this type of discomfort. It is believed that pain and a discernible decline in motor function follow from this. Maniwa et al. (2013) reported that those who use smartphones had a tendency to assume and sustain a forward-flexed head and neck posture. One of the main contributing causes to the prevalence might be the prolonged and/or frequent usage of these gadgets combined with a noticeably bent head position. More reliable observations have been made about the impact of smartphone usage duration on neck flexion and higher cervical angles. The given data generally indicates a positive association between the length of use and the neck and upper cervical flexion angles. Still up for debate, though, is the time frame associated with this increase in flexion angles. In contrast to Kim et al. (2015), who claimed that the increase occurred in less than five minutes, Park et al. discovered that the increase was substantial only after five minutes (or 300 seconds) of smartphone use. Furthermore, it is also unclear what use threshold users must reach before they start to feel pain and discomfort. For instance, one study determined that the lowest amount of time was 10 minutes. Everyday life was severely disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic virus in 2019. There were signs of this, including depression and anxiety, as well as negative impacts on the musculoskeletal system. The World Health Organization (WHO) designated COVID-19 as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern, resulting in travel restrictions and social immobility as a result of the epidemic. Worldwide public health organizations used varying degrees of lockdown to assist contain and restrict the spread of COVID-19. Beginning with the first lockdown in 2020, education moved from actual classrooms to virtual spaces. Furthermore, duties have to be done digitally for individuals as well. People's lives and actions were inevitably affected by this. Though it's possible that the lockdown had a negative effect on people's musculoskeletal systems, it turned out to be an effective way to stop the COVID-19 virus from spreading.12-14

It is well known that individuals frequently have neck discomfort, with an annual incidence rate of around 30%. Five out of ten individuals have neck pain on a daily basis, which is extremely dangerous for their health. The significant prevalence of neck pain may eventually be related to the prolonged usage of non-neutral spinal postures in workplaces and educational settings. One of the most common bad sagittal plane postures is the forward head position. With further loss of cervical spine extension, it has been proposed that this forward position may be playing a role in the development and maintenance of neck and back pain disorders.15

There have been several studies conducted to address the link between neck discomfort and forward head posture when using smart portable devices due to its growing therapeutic significance. That's why using smart portable gadgets has been connected to the development of neck discomfort because of this forward head posture. Users often use one or two hands below eye level to operate the gadgets. Pressure is applied to the cervical extensor muscles as a result of this display location's tendency to cause a more constrained head and neck position. Prolonged head flexion-related spinal morbidity and the ensuing physical strain on the neck among computer users have been well-researched. Weekly computer use has been linked to habitual spinal postures, according to a 2007 research study. Additionally, increased head and neck flexion angles in men were associated with computer usage, but increased lumbar lordosis was found in women. This illustrates how different genders' postures when utilizing digital devices varies.

Some small-scale studies have examined how people's posture varies when using their phones. Participants

The Research of Medical Science Review

were reported to maintain a head flexion angle ranging from 33 to 45 degrees from the vertical plane when staring at a mobile phone. Compared to users without discomfort, those with mild neck pain had more significant neck flexion angles. 12

The prevalence of neck discomfort is rising in society; it affects people of all ages, but is higher in young adults because of factors including prolonged computer and phone usage, desk job, bad posture, stress, and a decline in physical activity. According to a research done on college students 58.3% of the subjects had neck discomfort after a year. Neck pain can make daily tasks more difficult, lower productivity at work, and lower general quality of life. Psychological issues such as worry, depression, and sleep disturbances can be brought on by persistent neck discomfort. Research on the subject has increased as a result of the effects of neck discomfort on productivity at work and medical costs. There is a sizable amount of research on the connection between neck discomfort and neck muscular endurance. Although academic opinions on the relationship between neck discomfort and neck muscular endurance vary, experts generally agree that this aspect plays a significant role as a contributing factor. Sustaining the cervical spine and keeping it in place requires sufficient strength in the neck flexor and extensor muscles. Lack of endurance in these muscles might result in problems stabilizing the neck segments and inadequacies in supporting the cervical vertebrae. Extended lengths of time spent in static positions, such as spending a lot of time at a computer, can lead to neck muscular overuse. Long-term phone usage has been linked to pain, according to Lee et al., underscoring the significance of muscle endurance. Studies have demonstrated that those with neck discomfort have much reduced neck muscular endurance. The cervical vertebrae may experience aberrant stresses as a result of weak neck muscles that make it more difficult to maintain postural stability. The fact that the pathophysiology of neck pain may be significantly influenced by the neck muscles' lack of endurance lends credence to the research findings. Reduced proprioception and decreased extensor muscle endurance have been seen in those with persistent neck pain. Studies have revealed that cervical deep flexor muscles, in particular, are frequently slow to contract when there is cervical discomfort, which can exacerbate the condition. Nevertheless, no decline in endurance or rise in tiredness was noted in a research done on people with postural neck discomfort. It is proposed that systematically implementing exercise programs to build neck muscular endurance might be a useful tactic in the management or prevention of neck discomfort, even with the inconsistent findings in the literature. For the purpose of preserving and enhancing neck health, increasing the neck muscles' endurance may be a key tactic. According to research, neck discomfort can occur as a result of delayed activation of their muscles of the cervical area in particular. Nevertheless, no decline in endurance or rise in tiredness was noted in a research done on people with postural neck pain. It is proposed that methodical exercise regimens to build neck muscular endurance may be a useful tactic in the prevention or treatment of neck pain, despite the inconsistent findings in the research. Developing the neck muscles' endurance may be a key tactic for preserving and enhancing neck health. The importance of digital platforms and mobile phones in the post-pandemic era is growing. It is well known that these devices were introduced into universities after the pandemic. This is supported by the fact that the average amount of time spent on mobile phones each day has increased¹⁸. Recent studies have shown a link between rising mobile phone usage and an increase in cases of neck pain¹⁹. A comprehensive review of the literature that looked at risk factors for neck pain in university students has found a strong link between long-term use of electronic devices and the development of neck pain. According to the research, using electronics for longer than three hours a day is a major risk factor. Prolonged use of a cell phone might cause locked head and neck postures that put more strain on the spine and muscles of the neck. In the modern period, as cell phone usage becomes more commonplace, there is a greater chance that posture may deteriorate as muscle receptors adjust to this new environment. The neck muscles may become too strained and tense if you often tilt your head forward to look at your phone. Over time, neck pain may develop as a result of increased strain on the ligaments and discs between the cervical vertebrae caused by prolonged usage of mobile phones. Muscle imbalance can result from a flexion posture in the cervical and thoracic areas caused by the forward head position. Neck pain may worsen if you engage in static upper extremity tasks like using a phone while keeping this position. The research does not provide enough information about the connection between phone usage duration and neck muscular endurance as causes of neck discomfort in college students. In order to determine whether there is a relationship between university students' neck discomfort, neck muscular endurance, and the amount of time they spend using their phones, this study will look at these variables.¹

The purpose of the current study is to investigate the prevalence of the tension neck syndrome among

The Research of Medical Science Review

young smart phone users the study aims to determine possible factor associated with tension neck syndrome among smartphone users. The finding of this study can produce important information for exploring frequency and severity of tension neck syndrome among users and the association between intense smart phone use and tension neck syndrome.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Participants.

This study is a cross-sectional survey conducted in the University of Balochistan, Quetta Pakistan. This study was carried out from July to November 2024. The participants of this study were students who are more prone to mobile phone addiction age limit above 18 and using mobile phone for at least 5 hours a day having their own mobile.

Students were excluded with upper limb, neck and postural deformities due to any accident or congenital disorders. Those who had to perform any surgery related to neck upper limb and vertebral Column, students younger than 18 years and those not having their own mobile phone or use mobile phone for less than 5 hours. Students participated this study through the Google form voluntarily approached through official groups in social media. The local ethical committee at the Faculty of Rehabilitation approved this study on 22 June 2024.

Questionnaire and scale for assessment.

The data was collected from the participants through Neck Disability Index and Mobile Addiction Scale. There were four portions of this form first was a brief introduction about this study inclusion and exclusion criteria was mentioned in it, second portion was about demographic data age, gender etc. Third portion was Neck Disability Index questions in which the patricians were asked to select a most relevant statement of relevant question each of the statement was having specific score and same as NDI, Mobile Addiction Scale was having questions about mobile phone usage time and their most frequent position to assess the degree of neck flexion while using mobile phone. The total score of NDI was 50 and the score obtained by participant was converted into percentage and the level of disability was measured.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL. 41, 45

NDI (neck disability index)	Neck Disability
Mobile Addiction Scale (MAS)	Time spent on mobile.

Sample Size Estimation.

The sample size was calculated through Rao Software according to the reference article which was 250 and 172 at least.

Statistical analysis.

SPSS version 27 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). One way Anova test was used to find out correlation between Neck Disability and mobile phone addiction the significant P value was less than 0.05 which shows correlation among them.

The Research of Medical Science Review

RESULTS

The study was conducted based on sample size of 175. Table 1.1 shows the frequency of participant's age group, 18 years is 3 (1.7%), 19 years 8 (4.6%), 20 years 23 (13.1%), 21 years 43(24.6%), 22 years 16 (9.1%), 23 years 23(13.1%), 24 years 20 (11.4%), 25 years 14(8.0%), 26 years 3(1.7%), 27 years 10(5.7%), 28 years 3(1.7%), 29 years 2 (1.15%), 30 years 2(1.1%), 31 years 2(1.1%), 32 years 2(1.1%) and 33 years 1(0.6%). The table 1.2 shows the frequency of female participants is 108(61.7%) and the frequency of male participants is 67(38.3%) out of total 175 participants. Table 1.3 shows the frequency of individuals having minimal disability is 95 (54.3%), 58 (33.1%) with moderate disability, 20 (11.4%) with severe disability, only 2(1.1%) of them were in the crippled stage. In the table

1.4 show the frequency of average time period (in hours) using mobile phone in a day, 117(66.9%) were those who use mobile phone 5-7 hours daily, 42(28%) were those who use mobile phone 8-10 hours and only 16(9.1%) of them were using mobile for more than 10 hours. Table 1.5 shows the frequency of average time (in hours) using mobile phone for study in a day, 133(76%) use mobile phone for study 2-4 hours daily, 31(17.7%) use mobile phone for 5-7 hours daily for study and only 11(6.3) uses phone for more than 10 hours a day for study purposes. Table 1.6 shows the frequency of mobile phone users holding in both hands and one hand, 88(49.7%) uses mobile phone in both hands and 88(50.3%) uses in one hand. Table 1.7 shows the frequency of individuals experienced neck pain before, 95(54.3%) responded "yes" and 85(45.7%) responded "No" to the question. Table 1.9 shows the frequency of common position used while using mobile phone, 39(22.3%) uses mobile on side lying position, 52(37.6%) uses mobile phone in straight lying position and most of them 79(45.1%) uses mobile phone in sitting position. Figure 1.3 shows that the highest number of participants are having minimal or no disability, then those who were having moderate disability, few of them were having severe disability only 2 of them were in crippled stage. Figure 1.5 shows that most of the participants were using mobile phone for 5-7 hours, then those who were using them for 8-10 hours and only few of them were using it for more than 10 hours.

Table 1.9 shows the results of the NDI variable and time duration variable, the significant value was $>.001$ which means the co-relation between them as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Correlation significant test

The Research of Medical Science Review

	Frequency	Percent
Valid	18	3
	19	8
	20	23
	21	43
	22	16
	23	23
	24	20
	25	14
	26	3
	27	10
	28	3
	29	2
	30	2
	31	2
	32	2
	33	1
Total	175	100.0

Table 2: Validity performance

	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Female	108
	Male	67
	Total	175
		61.7
		38.3
		100.0

The Research of Medical Science Review

Table 3: Frequency of minimal disability

		Gender	
			Percent
Valid	0%-20% minimal disability	95	54.3
	21%-40% moderate disability	58	33.1
	41%-60% severe disability	20	11.4
	61%-80% crippled	2	1.1
Total		175	100.0

Table 4: Average time do you spend using your mobile device? (in hours per day)

The Research of Medical Science Review

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	5-7 hours	117	66.9	66.9	66.9
	8-10 hours	42	24.0	24.0	90.9
	more than 10 hours	16	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	175	100.0	100.0	

Average time do you spend using your mobile device? (in hours per day)

Average time do you spend using your mobile device? (in hours per day)

Table 5: How many hours do you spend on your device studying? (hours)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2-4 hours	133	76.0	76.0	76.0
	4-6 hours	31	17.7	17.7	93.7
	More than 6 hours	11	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	175	100.0	100.0	

The Research of Medical Science Review

Table 6: Do you hold your mobile in one hand or both hands when you use it (One hand, two hands)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Both hands	87	49.7	49.7	49.7
	One hand	88	50.3	50.3	100.0
	Total	175	100.0	100.0	

Do you hold your mobile in one hand or both hands when you use it (One hand, two hands)

Table 7: Frequency of one and both hand sides

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	No	80	45.7
	Yes	95	54.3
	Total	175	100.0

The Research of Medical Science Review

Did you experience neck or shoulder pain before? (Yes, No)

Table 8: Frequency of shoulder pain

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Lying on side	39	22.3
	Lying straight	57	32.6
	Sitting	79	45.1
	Total	175	100.0

Table 9: ANOVA Neck Disability Index

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.718	2	1.359	2.555	.001

The Research of Medical Science Review

DISCUSSION

The current study shows that all of the participants are age between 18-33 years, all were university students, the highest number of participants were aged 21 years and then 22 years old, the prevalence of neck disability in this study with moderate to severe disability according to NDI scoring was slightly more than the study conducted by Namwongsa et al in 2018 among students of University in Thailand.⁴²

The study found that a considerable portion of participants said they used their phones for five to seven hours per day, and many of them reported using them for several hours every day. Long-term use of mobile devices, particularly when held in non-ergonomic positions, is known to cause a number of musculoskeletal issues. Neck pain is one of the most prevalent problems linked to excessive phone use, and it is frequently made worse by a tendency of tilting the head downward while using a device. This posture, which involves keeping the neck flexed for extended periods time, puts excessive strain on the cervical spine and surrounding muscles, resulting in stiffness, and neck pain particularly in TNS. Furthermore, excessive screen time has effects that go beyond musculoskeletal health. Long-term screen time has also been linked to poor posture, which can cause a general misalignment of the spine and exacerbate chronic pain and discomfort, according to studies. Poor posture over time can cause the body to change structurally permanently, making it more difficult for people to recover from these. Ata Elven et al in 2024 conducted study and the conclusions show a strong correlation between the amount of time spent on a phone, muscle endurance, and neck pain. According to comparative research, students who use their phones for more than four hours a day report feeling more pain and having less endurance in their flexor muscles. It is recommended that ergonomic treatments be put in place for people who use phones for extended periods of time, and that the amount of time spent on phones each day be included in the evaluation of neck pain. Nonetheless, there is also a clear need for better neck alignment when using a phone as well as thorough instructions on how to utilize a phone every day.¹⁶

The most popular phone-using position among participants was sitting, which was followed by side and straight lying they can cause tension and discomfort if held for longer periods of time particularly if the neck is not supported or the posture is incorrect. People's physical well-being is greatly influenced by how they sit, lie, or recline when using their phones. If these frequent positions are not performed correctly, they might result in several musculoskeletal problems. People frequently slouch or lean forward, which puts extra strain on the spine, especially the neck and lower back. In particular, slouching causes the spine's natural curvature to be lost, which can put stress on the back's supporting muscles and ligaments.

These results emphasize how crucial it is to keep a good posture and make sure the body is properly supported when using mobile devices. The body can be less stressed by making small changes like sitting with the feet flat on the floor, shoulders relaxed, and the back straight. The chance of acquiring chronic musculoskeletal problems can also be decreased by taking regular breaks to stretch, shift positions, and exercise. In 2024 Agata Czępińska et al concluded that Cervical pain-related dysfunctions may impact students' learning capacities and, consequently, their development of professional capabilities. It is advised to avoid using a smartphone right before bed because it impairs focus and most of the participants addressed mobile usage in sitting position. Disability increases with the amount of time spent on the phone.^{43, 44}

The results of the study are mostly derived from participant self-reported information about their degrees of disability, neck pain, and mobile phone use. Although self-reporting study has a drawback One significant drawback is the possibility that individuals will overestimate or underestimate how much time they spend on their phones or how bad their neck pain is. Because of forgetfulness or lack of awareness. Comparing data across participants can be difficult since different people may interpret and experience pain in various ways. Others may intentionally or unintentionally overstate their pain or impairment levels, these disparities may result in inaccurate data, particularly when it comes to the actual incidence and severity of musculoskeletal problems associated with cell phone use.

Objective measurements would be crucial to gain a more thorough and accurate knowledge of the connection between cell phone use and neck pain. A more accurate picture of how much time users are actually spending on their phones, free from the biases of self-reporting, can be obtained by tracking actual screen time using wearable technologies or mobile apps. This technology may also provide information about how participants hold their phones and position their bodies when using phones.

These tools would give researchers more accurate information about how long and how often phone use relates to neck pain and other musculoskeletal problems by collecting data over an extended period of time

The Research of Medical Science Review

and analyzing pain patterns in relation to phone usage.

The issue of recall bias, which arises when individuals forget or are unable to accurately recollect their acts or experiences, would also be addressed with the use of objective measurements. Researchers might obtain a more accurate and comprehensive record of screen time and pain-related symptoms with continuous data from wearable devices, allowing them to pinpoint more exact relationships between the two. In 2024 Kassem El Shunnar stated that research that uses retrospective cross-sectional methods may be biased for a number of reasons. First, social desirability may have influenced the respondents' answers. Consequently, the data was collected in an anonymous manner. Second, reporting may have been impacted by current feelings or cognitive processes. It's possible that their most recent experience was more significant or vivid than others. Lastly, a larger sample size is desirable for the results of the current study to be generalized. Confounding aspects should be looked at and taken into consideration. Future research recommendations should take these problems into consideration.¹²

The study did not establish causation, but it was useful in showing a large correlation between cell phone use and neck pain. The results could have been distorted by a number of confounding factors that could have affected the observed correlation. A potential confounding element is the presence of pre-existing musculoskeletal conditions. When using a cell phone, for example, participants who already have chronic neck pain, arthritis, or other spine-related problems may be more likely to experience worsened discomfort. Posture is another potential confounding factor. People who already have bad posture—whether from desk job, sedentary lifestyles, or general inattention—are more likely to use their phones in an ergonomically unfriendly manner. People who don't regularly stretch or strengthen their necks and backs may have less neck and back muscle tone and flexibility, which makes them more prone to discomfort. Furthermore, it is challenging to draw firm conclusions regarding the direction of causality because the study's cross-sectional methodology only collects data at a single point in time. Although a high correlation between phone use and neck pain was found, the study is unable to determine whether phone use directly causes neck pain or whether those who have neck discomfort are just more prone to use their phones in ways that make their symptoms worse. The study highlights a significant possible connection between cell phone use and neck pain, its methodology precludes the discovery of a causative relationship. In 2023 Mikhled Falah Maayah stated in study that Despite the valuable information, this study has many drawbacks. The study discovered strong correlations between the assessed independent variables since it employed a cross-sectional methodology. Additionally, a large number of independent variables under evaluation are self-reported, which could introduce biases. The results of the study cannot be extrapolated to larger or comparable populations because the data were collected by convenience sampling. Additionally, the use of desktop computers and other study-related electronic devices was not taken into account by the researchers in the current study. Although there was potential for more volunteers, we were unable to come up with more than those selected for the study due to time constraints.²⁰

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the current investigation, about half of the individuals had neck issues. Neck issues were substantially correlated with smartphone addiction. Postural education and other initiatives to raise awareness of responsible smartphone use are advised. Participating actively in sports, social activities, and physical activity during free time will help university students reduce smartphone misuse and the effects it has on neck pain. Future research is necessary to determine how well neck posture-promoting strategies work to lessen smartphone addiction and misuse, which in turn helps to relieve neck pain.

LIMITATION OF STUDY:

Because it is a cross-sectional study, data is only collected once, making it difficult to establish a causal relationship between variables like neck pain, mobile phone use, and impairment levels. It is unclear from the associations found whether using a cell phone led to neck pain or impairment or the other way around.

Due to memory loss or social desirability bias, participants' self-reported mobile phone usage and other activities may contain errors.

Due to the small sample size of 175 people, the findings might not apply to broader demographics. It's also possible that the study doesn't accurately reflect a variety of demographic groupings outside the sampled population.

Certain characteristics, like neck pain and mobile phone usage, were the focus of the study. Other possible

The Research of Medical Science Review

contributing factors were not taken into account, such as pre-existing medical issues, physical activity levels, or ergonomic situations.

Potentially skewing the results could be the result of participants being chosen or volunteering in a way that is not representative of the general population.

Older age groups were underrepresented in the survey, which mostly targeted younger people. This restricts how far the results may be applied to other age groups

The study is unable to evaluate long-term effects of mobile phone usage habits on neck pain and disability or changes over time without follow-up data.

Self-Reported Disability Levels as a Basis

Self-reported assessments may inject subjectivity into the assessment of impairment and compromise the accuracy of the findings.

Recognizing these limitations means that the study's results should be interpreted with caution and that more research, ideally using longitudinal designs, should be done to better understand the connections between neck pain, impairment, and mobile phone use.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

For Researchers:

More Studies on the Use of Mobile Phones and Disability:

Perform long-term research to investigate the link between extended use of a mobile phone and physical impairments such neck pain and other musculoskeletal problems.

Examine the effects of heavy mobile phone use on the mind and body.

Investigate ergonomic measures to lessen the negative consequences of extended cell phone use.

Give special attention to investigating the mobile phone usage patterns and associated health issues of the 21-year-old age group, since they demonstrated the highest frequency of participation.

Examine whether the increased use of mobile phones by younger age groups (18–22) makes them more susceptible to impairments.

Analyze the differences in the effects of using a mobile phone for educational reasons versus for leisure.

Provide suggestions on how to minimize the physical risks associated with using a cell phone for study purposes.

For physiotherapists

Programs for awareness and preventive measures:

Patients should be made aware of the dangers of using cell phones for extended periods of time, especially when they are lying unnaturally (e.g., side-lying and straight-lying).

Encourage the use of phones at eye level and minimize one-handed use by promoting ergonomic usage habits.

Posture correction and exercise:

To reduce pressure on the shoulders and neck, promote frequent stretching exercises.

Plan therapy sessions for patients who have moderate to severe cell phone-related difficulties. Suggest ergonomic tools and posture correction methods to ease shoulder and neck strain.

Screen-Time Therapy:

Promote timed and restricted cell phone use, especially for those with severe or incapacitated stages of disability.

For Public

Establish Good Mobile Usage Practices: Avoid using your phone for more than five hours a day since this greatly raises your risk of neck pain and incapacity.

When holding a cell phone, use both hands to spread the strain equally.

Maintain Good Postures: Steer clear of spending a lot of time resting your phone on your side or upright. It is preferable to sit with the gadget at eye level. Stretch and relax your neck and eyes every 20 to 30 minutes.

Put an emphasis on purposeful use: To reduce needless screen time, give study or productive tasks on your phone priority over leisure use.

Children should be taught efficient screen time management techniques by their parents and teachers. Getting help early can help you avoid permanent handicap.

The Research of Medical Science Review

REFERENCES:

- França, D.L.M., et al., *Tension neck syndrome treated by acupuncture combined with physiotherapy: A comparative clinical trial (pilot study)*. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*, 2008. **16**(5): p. 268-277.
- Fatima, M., et al., *Prevalence of Smartphone Addiction among University Students during Covid-19*. 2023.
- Mathias, D., J. Jacob, and M. J., *cross-sectional study on mobile phone usage among youth*. *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 2018. **4**.
- Alsiwed, K.T., et al., *The prevalence of text neck syndrome and its association with smartphone use among medical students in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia*. *Journal of Musculoskeletal Surgery and Research*. **5**.
- Namwongsa, S., et al., *Effect of Neck Flexion Angles on Neck Muscle Activity among Smartphone Users With and Without Neck Pain*. *Ergonomics*, 2019. **62**: p. 1-26.
- Basharat, A., et al., *Association of forward head posture with neck pain, cervicogenic headache, neuropathy, and neck mobility among university students: a cross-sectional study*. *Foundation University Journal of Rehabilitation Sciences*, 2023. **3**: p. 72-76.
- Khired, Z., *The Prevalence of and Factors Associated With Neck Pain Among Jazan Adult Population*. *Cureus*, 2022. **14**(8): p. e28008.
- Jun, D., et al., *Physical risk factors for developing non-specific neck pain in office workers: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 2017. **90**(5): p. 373-410.
- Kamal, S., et al., *Smartphone addiction and its associated behaviors among medical and dental students in Pakistan: A cross-sectional survey*. *J Educ Health Promot*, 2022. **11**: p. 220.
- Naeem, N.-i.-K., Z.-e.-F. Naeem, and A.Y. Anwar, *Smartphone usage and its associated behaviours among undergraduate medical students in Pakistan*. *Discover Education*, 2024. **3**(1): p. 86.
- Syed Nasser, N., et al., *A Cross-Sectional Survey on Smartphone Usage Pattern, the Level of Mobile Phone Dependence and Psychosocial Effects among Undergraduate Students in a Malaysian University*. 2020.
- El Shunnar, K., M. Afeef Nisah, and Z.H. Kalaji, *The impact of excessive use of smart portable devices on neck pain and associated musculoskeletal symptoms. Prospective questionnaire-based study and review of literature*. *Interdisciplinary Neurosurgery*, 2024. **36**: p. 101952.
- Chemnad, K., et al., *Smartphone Usage before and during COVID-19: A Comparative Study Based on Objective Recording of Usage Data*. *Informatics*, 2022. **9**(4): p. 98.
- Alsharif, M.A., et al., *Usage and attitude of medical students towards mobile medical applications during and after COVID-19 lockdown: repeated cross-sectional study*. *BMC Medical Education*, 2024. **24**(1): p. 233.
- Thorburn, E., R. Pope, and S. Wang, *Musculoskeletal symptoms among adult smartphone and tablet device users: a retrospective study*. *Archives of Physiotherapy*, 2021. **11**(1): p. 1.
- Elvan, A., et al., *The association between mobile phone usage duration, neck muscle endurance, and neck pain among university students*. *Scientific Reports*, 2024. **14**(1): p. 20116.
- Xia, W., et al., *Burden of neck pain in general population of China, 1990-2019: An analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019*. *J Glob Health*, 2024. **14**: p. 04066.
- Paleti, S.T., et al., *A cross-sectional study to estimate the prevalence of text neck syndrome among medical students in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Andhra Pradesh*. *MRIMS Journal of Health Sciences*, 9900: p. 10.4103/mjhs.mjhs_120_23.
- Mersal, F.A., et al., *Effect of Mobile Phone Use on Musculoskeletal Complaints: Insights From Nursing Students at Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia*. *Cureus*, 2024. **16**(3): p. e57181.
- Maayah, M.F., et al., *Neck pain associated with smartphone usage among university students*. *PLoS One*, 2023. **18**(6): p. e0285451.
- Shabbir, A., et al., *Association Between Mobile Phone Usage and Neck Pain in Medical Students of Islamabad Pakistan: A Cross Sectional Study*. *Journal of Bashir Institute of Health Sciences*, 2023. **4**.
- Azadvari, M., et al., *Associations between exposure to common technology devices and reported neck pain*

The Research of Medical Science Review

- among Iranian school-age adolescents: a cross sectional study. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, 2023. **24**.
- Pk, K., V. N, and M. Andrews, *Prevalence of Tension Neck Syndrome in Frequent Computer Users*. *Medical & Clinical Case Reports Journal*, 2023. **1**: p. 68-71.
- Sirajudeen, M.S., et al., *Prevalence of text neck posture, smartphone addiction, and its association with neck disorders among university students in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia during the COVID-19 pandemic*. *PeerJ*, 2022. **10**: p. e14443.
- Atakla, H.G., et al., *Tech Neck Syndrome: A global epidemic of the modern era among students at the University of Abomey Calavi in Benin*. *Interdisciplinary Neurosurgery*, 2023. **34**: p. 101812.
- Salameh, M.A., et al., *Prevalence of text neck syndrome, its impact on neck dysfunction, and its associated factors among medical students: A cross-sectional study*. *Work*, 2024. **79**: p. 1111-1119.
- Anand, B., S. Thakur, and P. Sharma, *Association between Discomfort and Fatigue around Neck Area due to Portable Electronic Devices in College Students*. *Journal of Exercise Science and Physiotherapy*, 2020. **16**: p. 16-22.
- Derakhshanrad, N., et al., *Neck pain associated with smartphone overuse: cross-sectional report of a cohort study among office workers*. *Eur Spine J*, 2021. **30**(2): p. 461-467.
- Kumari, S., R. Kumar, and D. Sharma, *Text neck syndrome: the pain of modern era*. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 2021. **11**(11): p. 161-5.
- Vitta, A.d., et al., *Neck pain and associated factors in a sample of high school students in the city of Bauru, São Paulo, Brazil: cross-sectional study*. *Sao Paulo Medical Journal*, 2021. **139**.
- Ayhualem, S., et al., *Burden of neck pain and associated factors among smart phone user students in University of Gondar, Ethiopia*. *PLoS One*, 2021. **16**(9): p. e0256794.
- Shaikh, A.A. and S. Kadrekad, *Impact of work from home in covid-19: a survey on musculoskeletal problems in it professionals*. *Int J Allied Med Sci Clin Res*, 2020. **8**(3): p. 497-504.
- Vitta, A., et al., *Neck pain and factors associated in university students: a cross sectional study*. *Ciência em Movimento*, 2020. **22**: p. 89.
- Behera, P., et al., *Neck pain among undergraduate medical students in a premier institute of central India: A cross-sectional study of prevalence and associated factors*. *J Family Med Prim Care*, 2020. **9**(7): p. 3574-3581.
- Chan, L.L.Y., et al., *The prevalence of neck pain and associated risk factors among undergraduate students: A large-scale cross-sectional study*. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 2020. **76**: p. 102934.
- P, S. and S. Tamboli, *Prevalence of Text Neck Syndrome In Young-Adult population*. *International Journal Medical and Exercise Science*, 2020. **06**: p. 749-759.
- Al-Hadidi, F., et al., *Association between mobile phone use and neck pain in university students: A cross-sectional study using numeric rating scale for evaluation of neck pain*. *PLoS One*, 2019. **14**(5): p. e0217231.
- Alsalamah, A.M., et al., *Evaluating the relationship between smartphone addiction/overuse and musculoskeletal pain among medical students at Qassim University*. *J Family Med Prim Care*, 2019. **8**(9): p. 2953-2959.
- Alzaid, A.N., et al., *The prevalence of neck pain and the relationship between prolonged use of electronic devices and neck pain in: a Saudi Arabia, cross-sectional study in Saudi Arabia*. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*, 2018. **70**(11): p. 1992-1999.
- Crilly, P., et al., *Community Pharmacists' Involvement in Research in the United Kingdom*. *Pharmacy*, 2017. **5**.
- Ahmed, S., et al., *Smartphone addiction and its impact on musculoskeletal pain in neck, shoulder, elbow, and hand among college going students: a cross-sectional study*. *Bulletin of Faculty of Physical Therapy*, 2022. **27**(1): p. 5.
- Namwongsa, S., et al., *Factors associated with neck disorders among university student smartphone users*. *Work*, 2018. **61**(3): p. 367-378.
- Czepińska, A., M. Zawadka, and P. Gawda, *Neck pain, disability and mobile phone usage among physiotherapy students - a cross-sectional study*. *Ann Agric Environ Med*, 2024. **31**(1): p. 125-130.
- Cagnie, B., et al., *Individual and work related risk factors for neck pain among office workers: a cross*

The Research of Medical Science Review

sectional study. European Spine Journal, 2007. **16**(5): p. 679-686.

Suresh, A., et al., *Impact of Smartphone Addiction on Neck Pain and Disability in University Students*. JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH, 2021.

